

THE METHOD OF PROJECTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

The article considers that the project method is a comprehensive teaching method that allows to build an educational process based on the interests of students, enabling students to show independence in planning, organizing and controlling their educational and cognitive.

One of the urgent problems in teaching a foreign language in college today is the need for students to apply their knowledge in practice. To achieve results, it is necessary to apply the project method in the educational process. The project method is a comprehensive teaching method that allows you to build an educational process based on the interests of students, enabling students to show independence in planning, organizing and controlling their educational and cognitive activities. The project method is always focused on the independent activity of students, individual, paired, group, which students perform for a certain period of time. This method is organically combined with the method of learning in collaboration, problem-based and research methods of teaching.

A foreign language has great opportunities to create conditions for the cultural and personal development of students. The social order of society in the field of teaching foreign languages puts forward the task of developing the student's personality, strengthening the humanistic content of teaching, more fully realizing the educational, educational and developmental potential of the subject in relation to the individuality of each student. Therefore, it is no coincidence that the main purpose of teaching foreign languages at the present stage of education development is the student's personality, who is able and willing to participate in intercultural communication in the language being studied and independently improve in foreign language speech activity.

Therefore, when teaching a foreign language, I use a personality-oriented approach, which is based on the method of projects and learning in cooperation. This helps to create a positive attitude to learning English, give an opportunity to study with passion and reveal the potential of each student. Applying this methodology in practice, I am guided by the methodological recommendations of a researcher in the field of modern technologies of teaching students, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences S.E. Polat.

When organizing students' project activities, it is necessary to know about some criteria that need to be taken into account in the work. When working on a project, the author should be prepared accordingly. The project is divided into three stages: preparatory, main and final. In accordance with the sign of the dominant method in the project, the following types of projects can be designated: research, creative, role-playing, informational, practice-oriented.

Let's consider each of them.

Research projects – these projects should have a well-thought-out structure, goals, relevance of the subject of research, sources of information, results. They are close to scientific research. And also students must meet the level of language training at a certain stage of training.

Creative projects – these projects do not have a well-developed structure and should be designed accordingly (video, essay, newspaper article, role-playing game, etc.).

Role-playing projects – these are projects with an open structure in which students assume roles determined by the content of the project and the specifics of the problem being solved (literary characters, fictional

heroes, etc.). The results of such projects may be outlined at the beginning of the project, and may manifest only by its end.

Information projects – these projects are initially aimed at collecting information about an object or phenomenon. The structure of such a project can be designated as follows: the purpose of the project, the subject of information search, sources of information. Such projects are often integrated with research projects and become an integral part of them, a module.

Practice-oriented projects – these projects differ in a clearly defined result of the students' activities of the project, which is necessarily focused on the social interests of the participants themselves. Such a project requires a well-thought-out structure, even a scenario of all the activities of its participants with the definition of the function of each of them.

Monoprojects – these projects are carried out within the framework of a single academic subject, from which the most complex topics with social, historical or regional themes are selected. As a rule, work on such projects involves the application of knowledge from other fields.

Interdisciplinary projects – these projects are carried out outside of school hours and may involve several subjects in order to solve a task that is significant for all project participants. Many creative groups with specific research tasks can take part in such a project.

Projects with open, explicit coordination – the project coordinator takes part in these projects directly, unobtrusively directing the work of students, organizing, if necessary, individual stages of the project, the activities of its individual participants, for

example, if you need to arrange a meeting at some official institution, conduct a survey, take an interview.

Projects with hidden coordination – in these projects, the coordinator acts as a full participant in the project. Well-known telecommunication projects can serve as an example of them. As for the nature of contacts, projects can be internal or regional, international.

International projects – representatives of different countries participate in these projects. They are of exceptional interest, since their implementation requires information technology tools.

Of course, in practice, most often we have to deal with mixed types of projects in which there are signs of research and creative. Each type of project has one or another type of coordination, deadlines, stages, number of participants. Therefore, when developing a project, it is necessary to keep in mind the signs and characteristic features of each of them.

Conclusion. The project methodology provides great opportunities for solving tasks such as overcoming inertia, fear of speaking a foreign language due to possible errors in speech. The project methodology develops students' independence, creativity, and activity, which are so necessary for them in the learning process. The use of this method really transforms a student from an object of study into a subject of educational activity. The teacher also acts as an assistant and consultant. It is also very important that students learn to cooperate while working on a project, and learning in cooperation brings up in them such moral values as mutual assistance, desire and ability to empathize, creative abilities are formed, that is, there is a continuous process of learning and education. The project method forms and improves the general culture of communication and social behavior in general.

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